

Brussels, 19 May 2025

COST 029/25

DECISION

Subject: Memorandum of Understanding for the implementation of the COST Action “Sustainable Thermoelectrics European Network” (SUSTENET) CA24120

The COST Member Countries will find attached the Memorandum of Understanding for the COST Action Sustainable Thermoelectrics European Network approved by the Committee of Senior Officials through written procedure on 19 May 2025.

MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING

For the implementation of a COST Action designated as

COST Action CA24120 SUSTAINABLE THERMOELECTRICS EUROPEAN NETWORK (SUSTENET)

The COST Members through the present Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) wish to undertake joint activities of mutual interest and declare their common intention to participate in the COST Action, referred to above and described in the Technical Annex of this MoU.

The Action will be carried out in accordance with the set of COST Implementation Rules approved by the Committee of Senior Officials (CSO), or any document amending or replacing them.

The main aim and objective of the Action is to establish a strong collaborative framework that enables sustainable advancements in TE technology, thus catalysing progress in both scientific research and industrial applications across a wide range of domains.. This will be achieved through the specific objectives detailed in the Technical Annex.

The present MoU enters into force on the date of the approval of the COST Action by the CSO.

OVERVIEW

Summary

The strategies outlined in the European Green Deal and the EU Action Plans on Critical Raw Materials and the Circular Economy highlight the need for a sustainable development of renewable energy ecosystems and the efficient use of resources to promote a decarbonized society. Thermoelectric (TE) technology is regarded as alternative and environmentally friendly technology for harvesting and recovering heat, which is directly converted into electrical energy, as well as for cooling, heating and hybrid applications. The TE technology indeed holds significant potential for sustainable energy practices and the integration of the TE systems could lead to a new era of energy efficiency and contribute substantially to the EU energy sustainability efforts. Although the range of applications that can benefit from the use of devices based on this technology is very wide, there is still a supply chain to be developed. SUSTENET will address this issue by accelerating collaborative interdisciplinary knowledge generation and engagement with industrial partners, maximizing impact through knowledge creation and transfer, conducting environmental impact assessments and promoting research excellence. Additionally, SUSTENET will promote career development through workshops, seminars, and training schools, and will engage in extensive dissemination activities to amplify the impact of the outcomes. To achieve these goals, SUSTENET will be organized into 4 interconnected working groups:

WG1 - Scaling Sustainability through Artificial Intelligence

WG2 - Applications and User Cases

WG3 - Business Development and Supply Chain

WG4 - Dissemination, Communication and Training

<p>Areas of Expertise Relevant for the Action</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Materials engineering: Solid state materials ● Materials engineering: Semiconductors, material growth, physical properties for materials engineering applications ● Other engineering and technologies: Sustainability for other engineering and technologies ● Materials engineering: Databases, data mining, data curation, computational modelling ● Physical Sciences: Semiconductors, material growth, physical properties (theory) 	<p>Keywords</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Thermoelectric Technology ● Renewable Energy Ecosystems ● Sustainable Development Goals ● Decarbonized society ● Knowledge Sharing
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Specific Objectives

To achieve the main objective described in this MoU, the following specific objectives shall be accomplished:

Research Coordination

- Promote innovations and sustainability in all topics associated with the TE technology supply chain.
- Identify key economic challenges, supply chain issues, environmental concerns and regulatory constraints and propose measures to overcome them. Only then will TE technology be considered a “bullet proof” technology with high TRLs.
- Identify new, sustainable and improved TE materials also through AI methodologies.
- Define and standardize properties measurement protocols.
- Identify the most promising TE applications by evaluating both the attained and necessary characteristics

of the modules, alongside environmental considerations throughout their life cycle.

- Understand the current and future growth paths of the TE business sector in Europe.
- Create outreach channels with relevant policy makers at national and European level to help integrate sustainable solutions into climate and energy policies, including the integration of TE technology.

Capacity Building

- Establish a robust and flexible pan-European network, bringing together a diverse group of stakeholders in the field of TE technology with the aim of promoting a comprehensive and unified strategy to bridge current gaps between theory and practice that will translate into the technological and scientific development of this technology.
- Maximize interdisciplinary collaboration to promote knowledge exchange among all stakeholders involved in the Action.
- Facilitate future research pathways and stronger industrial cooperation beyond the period of this Action, for long-term collaborative activity and preparation of future more specific collaborative projects, through the development of roadmaps for the creation of a “European Thermoelectric Centre of Excellence” and a “European Thermoelectric Industrial Association”.
- Engage YRIs to deepen their connections with their peers, improve their research and networking skills, empower them for leadership and thus ensure the growth of the TE community in the future.
- Promote knowledge exchange and access to resources through Short Term Scientific Missions (STSMs), prioritizing YRIs and PhD students, while supporting gender equality and geographic balance, ensuring fair representation and opportunities across the Action.
- Promote the visibility of the Action outputs via specific dissemination and communication activities, e.g., publishing technical articles, peer-reviewed papers, attendance to fairs and the organisation of fostering forums (the “SUSTENET Project Fostering Forums”) to engage new stakeholders interested in participating in the Action.

TECHNICAL ANNEX

1. S&T EXCELLENCE

1.1. SOUNDNESS OF THE CHALLENGE

1.1.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE STATE OF THE ART

The European Union's (EU's) commitment to global climate action under the Paris Agreement [1] is at the heart of the European Green Deal [2]. **The REPowerEU Plan and the revised Renewable Energy Directive have set new ambition goals to speed up the EU's clean energy transition** [3, 4]. These policies aim to make Europe the world's first climate-neutral continent by 2050, while boosting the economy, and ensuring a just and inclusive transition for all. **Low carbon technologies are fundamental for a smooth transition to a climate-neutral society by** providing a sustainable and clean alternative to fossil fuels, enabling the decarbonization of various sectors, including electricity production, as well as heating and cooling.

Thermoelectric (TE) conversion represents a promising contribution for achieving carbon neutrality goals [5-7], and interest in TE systems as a clean energy alternative is on the rise. This trend resulted in increased research investment aimed at developing novel materials and optimizing device architectures to enhance the viability and sustainability of TE technology in terms of efficiency, cost, recycling, life cycle and profitability [5, 8-10]. However, this has yet to translate into a relevant TE industry in Europe.

Thermoelectric technology: TE technology is based on the principles of thermoelectricity that combines two phenomena in a material, specifically, heat and electric transport leading to the capability to generate both heating and cooling effects and to produce electrical power [6]. This dual functionality makes this technology a versatile tool in various applications, ranging from temperature regulation to energy harvesting:

Power to heating/cooling (Peltier effect): Applying electric power to a TE system, results into a heat pump to cool or heat. Compared to conventional heating, ventilation, and air conditioning systems, thermoelectricity presents several advantages when applied to building services including great versatility, loss-less scalability and high reliability. The primary advantage yet, is avoiding the use of refrigerant fluids harmful to the environment.

Heat to Power (Seebeck effect): Almost all manufacturing processes, from steel to cement industries, generate heat (so-called "waste heat"), as do all machines, from combustion engines to microprocessors. The possibility of using TE systems to capture and directly convert this waste heat into electrical energy is a very attractive approach to improve the overall energy efficiency and thus promote a sustainable future.

Thermoelectric materials: From the material point of view, TE materials can be divided into 3 categories: inorganic, organic and hybrid [6, 11, 12]. Representative examples of the families of inorganic TE materials include chalcogenides, oxides, oxy-chalcogenides, skutterudites, intermetallics, clathrates, half-Heuslers, silicon-germanium alloys and metal silicides. Organic TE materials include carbon nanotubes, graphene and polymers (e.g. poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) derivatives). The combination of inorganic TE materials with organic TE materials allows the production of hybrid TE materials.

The efficiency of a TE material, i.e., the ratio between the heat flow and electric power generated/used, **is governed by its 'figure of merit'**, termed zT , expressed as $zT = S^2\sigma T/k$, where S is the Seebeck coefficient, σ is the electrical conductivity, T is the operating temperature and k is the thermal conductivity. The goal is to maximize zT , which means that high performance requires large S and low k , characteristic of non-metallic systems, in combination with high σ , more usually found in metals [8]. Consequently S , σ and k can be hardly optimized independently, representing a challenge in designing high-performance materials. In addition, the optimal performance is typically confined to a narrow temperature range. Therefore, TE materials are typically divided into 3 categories based on the operating temperature: low (25 °C – 300 °C), medium (300 °C – 500 °C), and high (above 500 °C). Current commercial modules consist of telluride-based bulk materials, specifically, Bi_2Te_3 , appropriately

doped to produce the required *n*- and *p*-type variants for the low temperature range. Representative TE materials for the medium and high temperature ranges are, respectively, Pb-Te and Si-Ge alloys. To meet current and developing needs, there are some key factors to take into consideration when selecting materials, such as geopolitical abundance, cost, performance, thermal stability, scalable production and availability of compatible *n*- and *p*-type materials. Advances in modelling methods, combined with the emergence of high-performance computing and artificial intelligence (AI), have strengthened materials screening to support experimental studies in identifying TE materials that meet these needs [10, 13]. However, a critical challenge in advancing the TE field is the lack of dependable and consistent data, since a wide range of zT values are typically reported for all relevant TE materials. Implementing a regular collaborative round-robin approach for sample exchange and calibration within the TE community could prove invaluable for confirming performance metrics.

Thermoelectric modules: A TE module is a robust and highly reliable solid-state energy converter with unique features: no moving parts, minimal maintenance, silent operation, and absence of production of environmental deleterious waste during operation [6]. It is made from several TE junctions electrically connected in series that consist of *n*- and *p*-type TE semiconductor materials. Thermally, these junctions are connected in parallel so that heat can flow through the TE materials. Electrical insulation on the hot and cold sides stabilises the junctions, completing the module. The architectures for conventional TE modules for cooling/heating and for power generation are conceptually the same. The focus of current research has been on scalability and reproducibility, module system efficiency, thermo-mechanical stability, thermal interface materials, and material joining. Recent trends and future perspectives point to the development of flexible, printed and tandem modules [14]. It is equally imperative to establish standardized methods within the TE community for precise evaluation of TE module performance [15]. To accurately assess key performance indicators such as open circuit voltage, maximum output power, and maximum power density, it is recommended to utilize identical module architectures. These architectures should have an equal number of legs and be tested under a consistent thermal condition for reliable comparisons. Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that there are only a limited number of companies commercialising Bi₂Te₃-based TE modules in Europe, which poses major threat to the supply chain for manufacturers and end users of TE systems.

Thermoelectric systems: TE systems consist of three main components: a heat exchanger on the hot side, the TE module at the core, and a heat sink on the cold side [8]. For these systems to gain widespread commercial acceptance, it is vital to prioritize cost-effective design without compromising efficiency. A comprehensive study of the cost-performance dynamics of TE systems revealed that the most significant factors influencing the overall cost are the expenses associated with the heat exchanger (€/W/K) and the heat flux on the TE hot side [16]. Considering that there are numerous factors that influence conversion optimization, this area still requires more in-depth studies to improve understanding and achieve high profitability of the systems.

The impact of thermoelectric applications in promoting sustainable development: TE technology has attracted significant attention due to its great potential for waste heat recovery (industrial, residential, transportation, etc.). For example, it is estimated that the energy lost as waste heat in industrial processes ranges from 20% to 50%, with the possibility of reaching up to 75% in energy-intensive sectors, such as steel or glass production [16]. Consequently, even partial recovery of this waste heat leads to considerable improvement in energy utilization and a substantial decrease in greenhouse gas emissions. This would not only contribute to environmental protection but also support the advancement of circular economy [9]. In addition, TE cooling technology plays a crucial role in heat dissipation for electronic products due to its high reliability and ease of miniaturization. Thus, the field of sustainable TE applications is vast and, in addition to those already mentioned, can be used for energy harvesting applications in buildings (e.g., windows), wearable technologies, geothermal fields, consumer-based electronics, internet of things (IoT) and sensor networks [6, 12, 14, 18, 19].

Thermoelectric technology market perspective: At present, the market demand for TEs is lower than anticipated, despite their reputation as a sustainable energy source with minimal maintenance needs. The significant cost of TE system power output per watt poses challenges to their industrial adoption, hindering their widespread application and affecting their practicality. A recent analysis showed that a substantial 82% of TE cost is attributed to the two-level packaging of the TE materials. Consequently, there is a considerable opportunity to enhance the economic viability of TE products through the industrialization and standardization of their manufacturing processes [20].

Considering all the above aspects, it is evident that **there are several restrictions on the widespread**

implementation of TE technology, since it is still mainly used in niche applications. **Therefore, it is essential to create a pan-European TE network involving different stakeholders** (academics, researchers, innovators, standardization bodies and enterprises) for an integrated and holistic approach **able to strengthen the TE community and better understand, develop and promote the TE technology**. In this sense, the **SUSTENET Action is unique, as, to our knowledge, there is currently no other EU transnational cooperation project that covers the entire spectrum of TE technology**.

1.1.2. DESCRIPTION OF THE CHALLENGE (MAIN AIM)

Classical Bi₂Te₃-based materials have played an irreplaceable role in the TE field since the 1950s, yet these systems do not meet the standards and efficiency required for extensive application. In addition, **the dependence of current commercial TE systems on tellurium-based materials poses serious risks of supply chain disruption** due to its scarcity and geopolitical tensions [21]. As a result, these solid-state energy converters have not yet gained widespread penetration in the context of the climate crisis and related global energy challenge. Therefore, **sustainable large-scale implementation of TE technology requires addressing the replacement of tellurium-based TE materials**. In general, aspects connected to costs and sustainability have been little explored even for telluride-based systems. Namely, there is still limited knowledge on the cost-efficiency ratio and recycling processes, including a comprehensive analysis beyond just the constituent TE materials, as required for a circular economy. There is also lack of research on the economic implications of external factors such as refrigeration systems, connection between modules, and the operational environment. In short, the challenges encountered in the development of industrial TE production are numerous and the field is complex and multidisciplinary. TRL 9 has not yet been achieved in many applications, the technology is still largely economically unfeasible, and the user cases must be strengthened. Additionally, the environmental risks associated with commonly used toxic materials in TE fabrication and the exploration of abundant, low-cost alternatives have not been sufficiently addressed. Consequently, **the challenges associated with the development of a sustainable TE technology can then be summarised in terms of the following topics:**

- **Efficiency:** Performance of TE materials in converting heat to electricity directly and reversibly.
- **Cost:** Economic viability and affordability of TE systems.
- **Life Cycle:** Environmental impact of TE materials throughout their entire life span. Assessment of the compliance of different classes of TE materials with the RoHS Directive has not yet been addressed [22].
- **Recycling:** Processes and methods for reusing materials at the end of their life cycle. A dedicated law to regulate TE recycling is needed. The Waste from Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) Directive [23] does not adequately address the specific needs of TE systems.
- **Profitability:** Financial returns associated with the use of TE technologies.
- **Market volume and market dynamics:** Currently, the TE market is driven by the segment of TE cooling and heating (in industries such as electronics and automotive) with an estimated global market volume of approximately 0.6 B€ [24]. Besides this, decentralized power forms a small and quite dedicated segment, mainly driven by power generation. It is expected that a few emerging market segments will evolve, e.g., combined heat and power or industrial waste heat (both pushed by the Green Energy Transition) or autonomous sensors in process industries (driven by IoT). Progressive evolution of these emerging markets will lead to higher growth and to a sound contribution to reduce net greenhouse-gas emissions.
- **Circular Economy:** Integration of sustainable practices that promote resource conservation and waste reduction in TE systems.

The Action will embrace a holistic strategy to address these current challenges, integrating a multi-faceted collaboration across research, education and training for knowledge dissemination, alongside the practical implementation in industry for technological advancement. This unified approach ensures a seamless transition of insights and innovations from theory to practice, fostering a robust ecosystem of continuous improvement and development.

1.2. PROGRESS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

1.2.1. APPROACH TO THE CHALLENGE AND PROGRESS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

There is an urgent need to accelerate the green transition. This involves, for example, adopting innovative technologies, promoting supply chain sustainability and circularity, improving the energy efficiency of processes and avoiding or reusing waste heat in many contexts. This is only possible

through significant changes, including strong investment and collaborative actions. In fact, the above challenges result in high risks that cannot be covered by a single institutional “player” (either academic research or industry). They can only be overcome through implementation of an international and multidisciplinary network providing the strong interactions, and innovative solutions beyond the state of the art. Such network must bring together different stakeholders (academics, researchers, innovators, standardization bodies, industrial suppliers and end users), as proposed in this Action. Thus, **the objective of the SUSTENET Action is to create an effective collaborative synergy to obtain results that sustainably advance TE technology, triggering progress in science and industry for broader TE applications.** To accelerate the evolution towards large-scale production and industrialization swiftly and effectively, **SUSTENET is driven by three key elements: (1) cross-disciplinary international cooperation, (2) technological advancement, and (3) training.** Together, **these elements will foster a central exchange of knowledge among the following research areas within the TE supply chain:**

- **Integration of Advanced Methodologies:** Utilizing advancements in AI and atomic simulation techniques to predict and design new TE materials with improved properties.
- **Sustainable Material Development:** Explore abundant, low-cost alternatives to traditional TE materials and focus on using green technologies, with minimal environmental impact, to process these materials. The implementation of a standardization platform for reporting material properties will also contribute to the advancement in this topic, as it will allow to overcome the current fragmentation regarding how properties are obtained and reported.
- **Advanced Device Design and Operation:** Explore novel materials-agnostic device design and operational modes, leveraging power density/cooling loads achievable by existing low-cost low-impact TE materials.
- **Cost-Effectiveness Analysis:** Investigating the economic implications of manufacturing processes and the cost-efficiency ratio of TE materials and systems to enhance their viability.
- **Recycling and End-of-Life Strategies:** Developing effective recycling processes and end-of-life disposal methods for TE materials and systems to promote a circular economy.
- **Comprehensive Life Cycle Assessment:** Conducting thorough life cycle assessments to evaluate the environmental impacts of TE systems from production to disposal.

Additionally, to help drive the progress in TE technology beyond the timeframe of this Action, it will be necessary to maintain partnerships and strategies to incorporate equity in the development of this technology. Only in this way will it be possible to ensure a broad industrial adoption, to overcome new challenges and to recognize its crucial role as a green technology. Therefore, **this Action commits to prepare and present a roadmap for the implementation of a “European Thermoelectric Centre of Excellence”**, a knowledge hub that will bring together various stakeholders to facilitate and accelerate the implementation of TE technology. In a complementary way, and focused on the industrial sector, **the Action will also prepare and present a roadmap for the implementation of a “European Thermoelectric Industrial Association”**, to continually advance TE technology through collaboration and standard setting. It is also necessary to **promote the level of social responsibility regarding the adoption of measures associated with the green transition.** This is only possible through the adoption of awareness measures aimed at all sectors of society. SUSTENET will contribute to this fundamental objective by improving public literacy.

1.2.2. OBJECTIVES

1.2.2.1. Research Coordination Objectives

The main research coordination objectives of the SUSTENET Action are as follows:

- Promote innovations and sustainability in all topics associated with the TE technology supply chain.
- Identify key economic challenges, supply chain issues, environmental concerns and regulatory constraints and propose measures to overcome them. Only then will TE technology be considered a “bullet proof” technology with high TRLs.
- Identify new, sustainable and improved TE materials also through AI methodologies.
- Define and standardize properties measurement protocols.
- Identify the most promising TE applications by evaluating both the attained and necessary characteristics of the modules, alongside environmental considerations throughout their life cycle.
- Understand the current and future growth paths of the TE business sector in Europe.
- Create outreach channels with relevant policy makers at national and European level to help integrate sustainable solutions into climate and energy policies, including the integration of TE technology.

1.2.2.2. Capacity-building Objectives

The primary long-term objective is to develop research capacity and collaboration among all COST countries, specifically targeting ITC and Young Researchers (YRs). Other objectives are as follows:

- Establish a robust and flexible pan-European network that brings together a diverse group of stakeholders in the field of TE technology, including academics, researchers, innovators and companies, with the aim of promoting a comprehensive and unified strategy to bridge current gaps between theory and practice that will translate into the technological and scientific development of this technology.
- Maximize interdisciplinary collaboration to promote knowledge exchange among all stakeholders involved in the Action.
- Facilitate future research pathways and stronger industrial cooperation beyond the period of this Action, for long-term collaborative activity and preparation of future more specific collaborative projects, through the development of roadmaps for the creation of a “European Thermoelectric Centre of Excellence” and a “European Thermoelectric Industrial Association”.
- Engage YRIs to deepen their connections with their peers, improve their research and networking skills, empower them for leadership and thus ensure the growth of the TE community in the future.
- Promote knowledge exchange and access to resources through Short Term Scientific Missions (STSMs), prioritizing YRIs and PhD students, while supporting gender equality and geographic balance, ensuring fair representation and opportunities across the Action.
- Promote the visibility of the Action outputs via specific dissemination and communication activities, e.g., publishing technical articles, peer-reviewed papers, attendance to fairs and the organisation of fostering forums (the “SUSTENET Project Fostering Forums”) to engage new stakeholders interested in participating in the Action.

2. NETWORKING EXCELLENCE

2.1. ADDED VALUE OF NETWORKING IN S&T EXCELLENCE

2.1.1. ADDED VALUE IN RELATION TO EXISTING EFFORTS AT EUROPEAN AND/OR INTERNATIONAL LEVEL

SUSTENET is an initiative that expands the collaborative efforts of several leading European academic, research and industrial entities in the development of materials and systems associated with TE technology. The Action also brings together collaboration with other entities outside Europe, thus focusing on strengthening the essential international cooperation necessary to achieve the proposed objectives. The network is structured and organized to include a broad spectrum of researchers and experts in the field, along with institutions equipped with an extensive array of facilities and equipment. This setup will enable effective responses to the challenges that come with this ambitious project.

Additionally, two scientific associations dedicated to the field of thermoelectricity are noteworthy: the “European Thermoelectric Society” (ETS) and the “International Thermoelectric Society” (ITS). These two international non-profit organizations promote collaboration and innovation in TE technology. Therefore, the objectives proposed for this Action complement those of the ETS and ITS. SUSTENET focuses on bridging academic innovation with industry, specifically assisting startups developing socially desirable TE commercial products in successfully navigating the “valley of death” and securing funding during the critical intermediate stages of the innovation process.

2.2. ADDED VALUE OF NETWORKING IN IMPACT

2.2.1. SECURING THE CRITICAL MASS, EXPERTISE AND GEOGRAPHICAL BALANCE WITHIN THE COST MEMBERS AND BEYOND

The foundations of this Action build on current and previous pan-European collaborative efforts in the area of solid-state TE technology, involving multiple universities, research entities and companies (with a special emphasis on SMEs). In this way, the **initial SUSTENET network brings together a diverse and multidisciplinary group of proposers** from a broad range of countries and sectors, with a strong focus on gender balance, early-career involvement, and international collaboration. Their expertise spans a wide range of R&D&I domains, including, for example, computational materials science, experimental materials science, standardisation, sustainable energy materials, renewable energies

systems, environmental and social sciences, as well as business entrepreneurs and industrial stakeholders. By participating in this Action, they commit to **generating the necessary engagement synergies that encourage the retention of the** aforementioned **critical mass**, which will allow generating new knowledge and, consequently, driving innovation in TE technology **across Europe**. Furthermore, **this Action also includes proposers from outside Europe**, increasing the degree of global cooperation necessary for an undertaking of this magnitude. . In addition to the individual know-how of the experts, the Action will benefit from the large-scale research facilities made available by the institutions to which they are affiliated, such as high-performance computing clusters, state-of-the-art materials synthesis and characterization facilities, TE module/system production and testing facilities and standard life cycle assessment tools. The wide geographic area represented by the Action participants will facilitate communication and dissemination of the progress to policy makers at national and European level and encourage national and intergovernmental endorsement to accelerate the transition to a low-carbon economy. Nevertheless, **SUSTENET also intends to function as a dynamic hub**, in the sense that it will always be receptive to the involvement in the different planned activities of new stakeholders external to the Action, either from other COST member countries or from non-COST member countries, thus improving the collective experience. This approach allows for a continuous influx of fresh perspectives and knowledge, promoting the collaborative spirit of the initiative. To accomplish that, the Action established a WG (WG4) that will also be responsible for carrying out specific outreach and communication activities to engage new stakeholders and increase the mass for building a holistic and inclusive network for the sustainable development of TE technology.

2.2.2. INVOLVEMENT OF STAKEHOLDERS

The central idea of this Action focuses on creating a network covering solid-state TE technology to promote information exchange and collaboration, to identify opportunities for synergy between different end-use sectors, connecting them to the academic sector and to all other relevant stakeholders. As previously stated in section 1.2.1, **the Action already brings together 4 different groups of relevant stakeholders**: academics, researchers, innovators, industrial suppliers and end users. During the implementation of the Action, the interaction between these groups will occur through their participation in the different tasks of the 4 WGs through physical/online meetings, e.g., for the Management Committee meetings or the WG meetings, and through other target initiatives, such as workshops, seminars/webinars, STSMs, international conferences, data exchanges and sample exchanges. However, the incorporation of additional relevant stakeholders to the Action activities, from the scientific community to industrial partners and from policy makers to the general public, will only be achieved through the implementation of a successful strategy for dissemination and communication. **This necessarily means adopting specific measures and strategies for each group** (see Table 1), **which can be described as follows**:

- **Scientific community (academics/researchers/Young Researchers/ PhD students)**: The significant outcomes achieved in the Action will be disseminated to the scientific community through peer-reviewed Open Access articles in prestigious journals and by presenting at relevant international conferences. YRs and doctoral students will be strongly encouraged to take an active role in specific Action activities, as detailed in sections 1.2.2.2 and 3.2.1.
- **Industry sector (SMEs, potential investors, trade associations), associations of cross-sector organisations and policy makers**: To engage this group effectively, active participation in fairs and in dedicated sessions of scientific conferences will be essential, primarily by organizing targeted sessions and exhibitions that focus on the Action. Also important will be the communication of the main outcomes in technical magazines. In addition, members of this group will be invited to participate in some of the workshops/forums/webinars to be organized by the Action so that convenient strategies can be mutually defined for better acceptance and integration of TE technology in society. This approach will not only foster interaction but also ensure that this group is fully immersed in the relevant activities and discussion.
- **General public (citizens and media)**: Engaging with the public across multiple media platforms is crucial for highlighting the progress and significance of low-carbon technologies, such as TE technology. It's essential to inform and educate people on the importance of embracing and integrating these technologies to foster sustainable societal development. This will be achieved through the publication of opinion articles and interviews in newspapers and magazines, radio, television, podcasts, educational videos and presence at other science outreach events (e.g., the European Researchers' Night).

A webpage is set to go live, designed to disseminate and communicate the Action objectives and initiatives. This website will serve as a hub for various stakeholders, offering customized content to meet different requirements. Additionally, strategic engagement through social media accounts will be employed to capture the interest of our target audiences.

3. IMPACT

3.1. IMPACT TO SCIENCE, SOCIETY AND COMPETITIVENESS, AND POTENTIAL FOR INNOVATION/BREAKTHROUGHS

3.1.1. SCIENTIFIC, TECHNOLOGICAL, AND/OR SOCIOECONOMIC IMPACTS (INCLUDING POTENTIAL INNOVATIONS AND/OR BREAKTHROUGHS)

The activities planned for SUSTENET, which relies on a solid pan-European multidisciplinary team made up of long-time experts in the different aspects associated with the TE technology value chain, **will give rise to the following outcomes:** (1) identify new and improved TE materials based on abundant and eco-friendly elements, (2) establish consistent protocols and reference standards for reporting material properties, (3) develop an Application White Paper (AWP), (4) develop a TE application database, (5) identify new application cases for TE technologies, (6) develop industrial standards for characterization and certification, (7) outline business opportunities, (8) report on "Trends in the European Thermoelectric Business Sector", (9) develop a comprehensive roadmap to establish a "European Thermoelectric Industrial Association", (10) elaborate a roadmap to establish a "European Thermoelectric Centre of Excellence". **Based on this, the Action is expected to achieve a wide range of important impacts for future sustainable TE technology, which can be described as follows:**

Scientific impact: The Action will foster a comprehensive understanding of the TE technology. It will carry out comprehensive curated databases from critical literature reviews on benefits and potential drawbacks of existing mainstream TE systems, serving as a valuable resource for a wider research community. By gathering an international group of experts in different domains, this action will bring together knowledge and know-how that will be valuable to develop an in-depth understanding of the physical chemistry of TE materials, devices, key technologies for processing and production, and sustainability aspects. The activities foreseen in the Action will also empower YRs to become future leaders in the field in the longer term. Additionally, the synergy conceived between the different groups of participants in the Action will encourage the creation of a platform capable of outlining new research projects and applying for competitive EU funding programmes for research and innovation.

Technological impact: The Action will contribute to the general optimization of TE systems, making them more efficient and sustainable across the broad spectrum of applications, whether for heating and cooling or power generation, thereby improving their functionality. It will also serve as a basis for new technological developments based on the integration of sustainable practices, e.g., for the identification, development and implementation of new high-performance TE materials based on abundant, non-toxic, and cheap elements with minimal environmental footprint. Similarly, these criteria will be the basis for the use of new technologies that deal with the processing and production of materials, devices and systems, while already established processes will be improved as well.

Socioeconomic impact and competitiveness: All participants involved in this Action aim to contribute to the effort of promoting Europe's sustainable development and competitiveness through the implementation of R&D&I and business activities, that in the specific case of the SUSTENET Action will contemplate the sustainability issues of the TE technology supply chain. The Action will have socioeconomic impact through the active involvement of industrial partners which will bring a Europe-wide increase in entrepreneurship associated with the TE technology. The outcomes of the Action can assist SMEs in creating optimised solutions that can be more competitive, stimulating the development of high-efficient TE modules and of new applications, diversifying and increasing the market, particularly at European level. This can also lead to the creation of new businesses and jobs.

General aspects related to the green energy transition will also be considered in this Action. **Aligned with the EU Agenda**, as anticipated in the European Green Deal and REPowerEU Plan, **as well with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 04, 05, 07, 09, 11, and 13), the outputs of the Action are expected to have a wide societal impact.** This will be achieved by promoting awareness and literacy among citizens, influencers and policy makers, which will contribute to improving society's perception of the sustainability of low-carbon technologies and the circular economy. In other words, it will make sure that the complexities behind the adoption of the green transition for society, economy, and culture are clear to everyone. It is essential to involve stakeholders across society – from individuals and local communities to enterprises and governmental bodies – since the shift towards sustainability will take place across all these sectors. The Action will facilitate this process by promoting educational activities to elucidate those complexities.

3.2. MEASURES TO MAXIMISE IMPACT

3.2.1. KNOWLEDGE CREATION, TRANSFER OF KNOWLEDGE AND CAREER DEVELOPMENT

Knowledge creation: SUSTENET contributes to knowledge creation by promoting, within a truly pan-European network, **a research agenda guided by industry and customer needs and fostering scientific developments within the current sustainable development scenario**, necessary to make solid-state TE technology more sustainable, widely understandable and available. The new knowledge that will be created will be obtained using excellent science, innovative AI methodologies and innovative technologies that will result in important guidelines and knowledge bases for the wider community (researchers and innovators/industry), outlining, e.g., new sustainable and high-performance TE materials, new application cases, recommendations for possible standardizations (including life cycle-based sustainability standards and guidelines) and, ultimately, in a true characterisation of the European TE business sector. Inherent to this knowledge creation is the necessary **interactive and synergistic interaction between researchers, innovators and SMEs**. This particularity **will be fundamental to closing the knowledge and communication gap, that often exists between these communities in Europe** and internationally, and to boost private investments in research, leading to more inventions and patents.

Transfer of knowledge: SUSTENET participants will make every effort to make research and innovation **results publicly accessible to all interested parties to ensure that the proposed solutions and guidelines translate into real benefits for society** and thus contribute positively to overcoming the needs and the current challenges that Europe faces. **This will be achieved in the following way: (1)** by fostering an ongoing exchange of knowledge between Action experts from both academia and industry - this premise is an integral part of the Action and cannot be left to chance; **(2)** ensuring that all type of produced publications (e.g., publications in high quality scientific journals, deliverables, databases, protocols/standards, technical reports and roadmaps) will be open to the public through Zenodo cloud-based storage platform; **(3)** dissemination at scientific events; **(4)** programming STSMs and training courses; **(5)** organising various other types of events tailored to specific stakeholders, like educational activities, workshops and webinars/seminars; **(6)** through the extensive pan-European network of countries, institutions and participants; **(7)** by encouraging all participants to further communicate the objectives and results of the Action to stakeholders at the national level in their respective languages for better understanding and outreach; **(8)** through the involvement of international partners that will enable bilateral knowledge transfer between Europe and other regions of the world. Experts from academia, industry and policy makers will be invited to share their knowledge and practices through lectures, seminars and tutorial supervision.

Career development: The pursuit of the European Green Deal's goals, which aim to steer Europe towards a sustainable development, presents a multifaceted challenge. This endeavour requires considerable investment and persistent collaborative efforts by experts from diverse disciplines, not only now but also in the years to come. Ensuring the commitment of YRIs and promoting an environment that promotes innovation is fundamental to this objective. In this sense, **the empowerment of the careers of YRs and innovators is at the essence of this Action**. This will be **based on the principles of gender balance and will be achieved in the following way: (1)** by supporting the proactive participation of YRs in the management tasks, e.g.,. In this way, they can acquire a diverse set of capabilities, such as those needed to develop and prepare new research initiatives and to collaborate in international networks; **(2)** by encouraging YRIs and doctoral students to take advantage of conference grant funding opportunities; **(3)** by actively promoting the temporary transfer of doctoral students and YRIs to the different laboratory facilities within the network, engaging them in STSMs.

3.2.2. PLAN FOR DISSEMINATION AND/OR EXPLOITATION AND DIALOGUE WITH THE GENERAL PUBLIC OR POLICY

The results and progress of the Action will be disseminated to diverse stakeholders through appropriate channels, as outlined in Table 1, and this process will be steered within WG4, whose activity is detailed in section 4.1.1. **The target audience extends beyond the Action's participants** to encompass international research communities, students, educators at both undergraduate and university levels, European and national energy communities/associations, industry associations, technology clusters, professional boards, policy makers, regulatory and standardization bodies, and the

general public (see also section 2). **A dedicated website and social media accounts will be established** within the first six months. They will serve to reach specific target groups (e.g. groups on LinkedIn) and a more general audience (LinkedIn for general business audiences and X for the general public and a few experts). The website and the social media will be used for rapid dissemination of public announcements, such as about workshops, training courses, and participant publications. A **YouTube channel** will host recorded seminars from workshops, educational videos, and other presentations like the webinars. The scientific and methodological advancements arising from novel “spinoff” collaborations between Action members will be disseminated to all interested stakeholders via presentations and journal articles, using the Action's media platforms to multiply the impact. **Zenodo is chosen as reference Open Access repository for the Action**, and a SUSTENET community will be hosted there.

Table 1 – Dissemination, Communication and Training channels, stakeholders and KPIs.

Action outcome/channel	Target audience	KPI
Website	Scientists, engineers, industry & public audience	Nr. of visitors: >2000 in total
Social media	Scientists, engineers, industry & public audience	LinkedIn page: >600 followers; LinkedIn + X: >20 posts/year
Participation at Conferences / Fairs	Scientists, engineers, industry, policy makers & public audience	Conferences/fairs: >=2/year; Presentations: >=5/year
SUSTENET Workshop and Training	Scientists, engineers, industry, policy makers & public audience, students, YRs	1/year Trainees: >100 in total
SUSTENET Project Fostering Forums	Scientists, engineers, industry, & policy makers	1/year
SUSTENET Webinars	Scientists, engineers, industry, policy makers & public audience, students, YRs	3/year
Publications (journals et similia)	Scientists, engineers, industry, policy makers and public audience	>20

4. IMPLEMENTATION

4.1. COHERENCE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF THE WORK PLAN

4.1.1. DESCRIPTION OF WORKING GROUPS, TASKS AND ACTIVITIES

In order to achieve the Action objectives and to ensure a pan-European knowledge exchange related to a sustainable TE technology, **SUSTENET is organized into 4 interconnected Working Groups (WGs)** (Fig. 1): WG1, focused on all sustainability perspectives of TE materials, systems and technologies predicted by AI; WG2, devoted to the applications, current and future trends in TE systems; WG3, dedicated to the commercialization and marketing aspects of TE technology; and WG4, focused on dissemination, communication and training activities. .

Figure 1: Pert diagram.

As set by the COST rules, the overall management of the Action will be led by the *Management Committee (MC)*. MC meetings will be held at least once per year, unless the interest of the Action requires intermediate meetings. In accordance with the established rules, WG Leaders (WGL) and WG Co- Leaders (WGCL) members will be elected at the first Kick-off meeting. A Core Group (CG) will be established which will report to the MC and be responsible for the day-to-day progress of the Action. The CG will be composed by the Action Chair, Action Vice-Chair, WGLs, WGCLs and other action

coordination positions. When appointing leadership positions, a balanced representation of genders and generations, along with equitable inclusion of individuals from ICT and non-ICT, will serve as the guiding criteria. The MC will meet with the CG every 6 months (one coinciding with the annual MC meeting and the other online) to map progress based on the WGs' reports and organize the network's activities for the next period, ensuring the implementation of the COST policy and the approval of the participation of additional entities from COST member or non-member countries and the management of the network's budget.

WG1 - Scaling Sustainability through Artificial Intelligence: One of the most important obstacles to large-scale implementation of TE technology in a wide range of applications is the lack of sustainable and economically affordable materials with beneficial TE properties. This WG is dedicated in identifying and developing new and improved TE materials and devices based on abundant, non-toxic, and cheap elements with minimal environmental footprint.

T1.1: Materials discovery. The TE literature has grown extensive, encompassing experimental and modelling studies, some of which have screened huge numbers of potential compounds. Contemporary AI techniques will be used to harvest promising compounds from the literature and online databases to create a curated library of promising, sustainable TE compounds for further experimental and theoretical studies. This will be corroborated by high-quality first-principles simulations.

T1.2: Standardisation of materials properties. A significant challenge within the TE community is the considerable variability in the reported properties of specific materials. TE behaviour is critically influenced by factors such as composition, impurities or dopants, crystal structure, and microstructure, and is also highly temperature dependent. As a result, the design and synthesis of TE materials require navigating the intricate interplay of these diverse parameters, often leading to a broad spectrum of properties and performance outcomes. Despite these complexities, the current state of TE materials design and synthesis has matured sufficiently, creating an urgent need for an internationally recognized standardization body to establish consistent protocols and benchmarks for reporting material properties. This standardization would enhance comparability and reliability within the field, promoting accelerated advancements in TE technology. SUSTENET will establish a roadmap for implementing a TE Standardization Platform to serve the TE community and contribute to the advancement of the field through consistent and reliable materials reporting and characterization.

WG2 - Applications and User Cases: The main objectives of WG2 will be the elaboration of a database listing Application-Material-Combinations (*AMC's*), a database of TE applications, the development of an Application White Paper (AWP) and the identification of new application cases for TE technologies. The activities outlined for WG2 will be carried out in a straight connection and communication with the activities of WG3.

T2.1: Evaluation and classification of Thermoelectric Applications and Materials. The major activity of this task will be to evaluate the previous and current status of TE applications and connect them to a down-selection of feasible material systems, leading to a list of *AMC's*. For all *AMC's*, found either from literature or from other sources, an overview of the status will be composed, containing information such as: material, processing routes, thermo-mechanical stability, TE performance, range of application temperatures, contact materials and demonstration of device integration with these materials. This information will be gathered in an open access database, evaluated by AI tools, and maintained and updated continuously. The information will be organized such that it will be accessible for the TE community. A preferred material system for each application will be recommended to stimulate alignment.

T2.2: Evaluation and assessment of Thermoelectric applications and use cases within the European community. The benefit of solid-state TE applications, and their relevance for the society and for the green energy transition are quite clear to members of the TE community, but unknown or unclear to most stakeholders in the non-TE community, including policy makers and the general public. On top of this, the relevance might vary from country to country, from region to region or from industry to industry. The most widely known applications are power generation, for the space industry, and TE cooling for the electronics industry. Within the activities of this task, a database of TE applications will be created, and each one will be evaluated according to industrial and social criteria, such as: its relevance to the end user, market deployment efforts and barriers, solution potential, green energy contribution, competitive solutions, integration of sustainable practices, life cycle, maturation timeline. To this purpose the working group will organize interactions and networking with active people and

organizations. A provisional list of applications to be considered for this analysis is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 – Provisional list of applications for the elaboration of a TE application database.

Thermoelectric Segment	Industrial application
Peltier cooling	Electronics, medical, air conditioner
Industrial waste heat recovery	Process industries (low temperature), heavy industries (high temperature)
Combined Heat and Power	Domestic biofuel heating systems
Decentralized power generation	Space, geothermal energy, defence and security
Temperature control at low temperatures	Cryogenic industries
Internet of things	Process industries, infrastructure

T2.3: Detailed classification of Specific Applications and Use Cases. In this activity, a restricted number of prioritized applications will be classified in detail. This contains the elaboration of an *AWP*, also including aspects like industry requirements, product standards and life cycle. These *AWPs* can be used as basis to enter into R&D and/or Industrialization programs, for the acquisition of commercial funding and to inform potential customers. To this end, interactions and networking will be established with interested stakeholders, including coordinators of ongoing projects and international associations/alliances.

Some examples of existing market segments for TE applications include: (a) sustainable TE cooling devices for refrigeration and on-spot air condition in cars; (b) thermal management of microelectronic, telecommunication and medical devices; (c) decentralized power generation for space missions and security needs. The largest market is the TE cooling segment with a turnaround of around 0.6 B€ per year. Two material systems with high TE (high zT) performance at room temperature and based on abundant elements will be identified from the activities developed in T1.1 and T2.1. The two selected materials will be integrated into TE modules for cooling and will be long-term tested and critically evaluated in comparison to commercial Bi_2Te_3 modules.

New market segments for TE applications: Within this activity, new application cases for TE technologies will be identify and investigate, which go significantly beyond the current module technology and might introduce disruptive innovations and new market potentials. Potential future use cases include: (a) cryogenic TE applications for cooling over temperature large differences of >150 K down from room temperature or TE generator powered by evaporation of liquid hydrogen and liquefied natural gas; (b) high-temperature waste heat recovery, with hot side temperatures > 500 °C from high-temperature industrial processes, which will require extremely robust TE materials, contacts, and novel module designs for the operation in very harsh environments; (c) flexible, miniaturized and integrated TE modules in textile, implants and microelectronics. This task will have an exploratory character that goes significantly beyond the current material development and module engineering of TE.

WG3 - Business Development and Supply Chain: This working group has the following objectives: to bring manufactures and suppliers related to TE on the same page, to provide a communication platform to clarify demands, to form industrial standards for characterization and certification, and to attract investors that are willing to accelerate the commercialization of TE. The planned activities for WG3 will be executed in close coordination and ongoing dialogue with the WG2 initiatives. For example, the list of TE applications to be created under WG2 will serve as a basis for creating a bank of ideas for potential business opportunities.

T3.1: Expertise database. With the aim of understanding the current and future growth paths of the TE business sector in Europe, this activity will result in an open database containing relevant information on the TE business sector covering European companies. This document will be prepared in the form of a comprehensive survey on “Trends in the European Thermoelectric Business Sector”. This document will include key elements such as market size, market maturity, production, whether sustainable practices exist to promote the circular economy, legislative regulations, and growth prospects.

T3.2: Matchmaking and outreaching. In close connection with T3.1 activities, set up a matchmaking mechanism to connect demands with supplies. Based on matchmaking results, propose business opportunities to grants and to relevant stakeholders through networking activities, like industry-specific seminar/workshop and virtual groups.

T3.3: Thermoelectric industrial association. Numerous companies across Europe are engaged in various aspects of TE materials, including material synthesis, module design & fabrication, and the deployment of TE systems. The formation of an association among these companies would be instrumental in promoting the growth and development of the industry by fostering collaboration, offering essential resources, advocating for member interests, and voice on key issues affecting the sector. To facilitate this effort, SUSTENET is committed to developing a comprehensive roadmap for establishing the European Thermoelectric Industrial Association. This association will serve as a catalyst for unity among industry players, driving innovation and enhancing the development and deployment of TE technologies throughout Europe.

WG4 - Dissemination, Communication and Training: The activity in this WG will support the Scientific Communication Coordinator and will focus on the outreach of the action, in terms of Communication, Dissemination and Training. It will make use of mostly online tools and selected in person activities, like workshops and participation in conferences. Networking and fostering of spinoff joint research activities will be prioritised. Educational activities will be carried out to promote awareness and literacy among the broad spectrum of stakeholders on sustainable development through the production of short videos, a comic story and participation in science fairs. A final Roadmap for legacy activities will be prepared and presented at the end of the Action.

T4.1: Online Tools. Establish and maintain an Action graphical identity, a website and social media accounts. Producing dissemination materials (factsheets, newsletters, review papers, technical notes, educational resources). Integrate a business-to-business matchmaking system on the website to facilitate networking and collaboration. Compiling information on external conferences, summer schools, internship opportunities, and job openings on the members-only SharePoint, including potential opportunities for collaboration arising from the exploitation of the results of the Action.. Create a Zenodo SUSTENET community for Open Access publication and storage.

T4.2: SUSTENET events. Organisation of an annual SUSTENET Workshop and Training (preferably in the last quarter of each year), featuring training courses designed for YRs, postgraduate students, PhD students, and Master's students to develop transversal skills, including metadata management, digital twins and device building, industrial-level scale-up production, sustainability-by-design, and national policy. The SUSTENET Workshop and Training will specifically include presentations by gender equilibrated YRs and participants from ITC. Dedicated sessions will be organised along with ETS/ITS in ECT/ICT conferences, and satellite events will be planned at other relevant conferences/events (e.g., the Raw Materials Week) to facilitate a higher participation. Publish the courses through the Action's online tools, in compliance with open science principles. Organisation of an (at least annual) series of SUSTENET Project Fostering Forums, in person or online, to involve new stakeholders and to stimulate the creation of consortia for funded R&D&I in TEs.

T4.3: SUSTENET legacy. The outcomes of the work to be developed by the activities planned in all WGs will culminate in the elaboration of a "SUSTENET Roadmap for a European Thermoelectric Centre of Excellence". This initiative will be of great relevance to strengthen European competitiveness in TE technology. The idea is to define a plan for creating a permanent platform for stronger collaboration between research organisations, industry and policy makers across Europe, where it will be possible to formulate the research needs of both academia and industry and provide the necessary solutions, not only for current problems, but also for the future. The roadmap for this Centre of Excellence, to be presented at the concluding SUSTENET Workshop organised in T4.2, will not only define the activities, but also propose measures on how they could be financed, and which will necessarily have to include collaborative research projects within a given co-funded research program.

The following tasks/activities encompassing all WGs are overseen by the MC and the CG members:

WG Webinars: Twice a year, dedicated webinars focused on a specific objective or deliverable will be organized for each technical WG (i.e., WGs1, 2 and 3).

Short-Term Scientific Missions (STSM): The Action plans to implement STSMs, aiming to a minimum of 4 annually, to promote the temporary transfer of its associated researchers to the different laboratory facilities available within the network. The target of these missions are YRs and doctoral students. At the same time, this initiative is designed to cultivate new partnerships, and to provide training and access to novel and specialized techniques that may be not available at the researchers' home institutions. To manage this process, the Grant Awarding Committee will evaluate the applications, and those selected will have their travel and subsistence expenses covered by the network during their stay.

Inclusive Target Countries Conference grants (ITC-CG): Grants for presentations at international conferences for doctoral students and YRs from ITCs. The approval of such grants is subject to certain conditions as duly specified in the COST Annotated Rules.

4.1.2. DESCRIPTION OF DELIVERABLES AND TIMEFRAME

The activities of the Action will result in 18 deliverables described below.

Deliverables		WG	Month (year/quarter)
Nº	Title		
D1	Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools	4	3 (Y1/Q1)
D2	Report of the first SUSTENET workshop and training on “Integrating Sustainability into Material Selection”	1, 2	12 (Y1/Q4)
D3	Report of the SUSTENET Project Fostering Forums held during year 1	1 to 4	12 (Y1/Q4)
D4	Report of the second SUSTENET workshop and training on “Exploring the Future of Thermoelectric Solutions”	1, 2	24 (Y2/Q4)
D5	Report on SUSTENET Project Fostering Forums held during year 2	1 to 4	24 (Y2/Q4)
D6	Review article on TE technology: from modelling to device development published	1, 2	28 (Y3/Q2)
D7	Application White Paper	2	35 (Y3/Q4)
D8	Report of the SUSTENET Project Fostering Forums held during year 3	1 to 4	36 (Y3/Q4)
D9	Report of the third SUSTENET workshop and training on “Thermoelectric Industry Supply Chain Analysis”	3	36 (Y3/Q4)
D10	SUSTENET Roadmap for a Thermoelectric Standardization Platform	1	42 (Y4/Q2)
D11	Report on Short-Term Scientific Mission for Young Researchers on modelling, experimental procedures and device fabrication of sustainable TE devices	1, 2	42 (Y4/Q2)
D12	Report on “Trends in the European Thermoelectric Business Sector”	3	43 (Y4/Q3)
D13	Review article on Evaluation of technological benchmarking and economic viability published	2, 3	45 (Y4/Q3)
D14	Report of the fourth SUSTENET workshop and training on “Evaluation and assessment of Thermoelectric applications and use cases within the European community”	2, 3	45 (Y4/Q3)
D15	Report on established links between academia and industry via joint project applications, collaborative articles, and established breakthrough scientific developments & new business opportunities	1 to 4	48 (Y4/Q4)
D16	Report on SUSTENET Project Fostering Forums held during year 4	1 to 4	48 (Y4/Q4)
D17	SUSTENET Roadmap for a European Industrial Association	3	48 (Y4/Q4)
D18	SUSTENET Roadmap towards a European Thermoelectric Centre of Excellence	1 to 4	48 (Y4/Q4)

4.1.3. RISK ANALYSIS AND CONTINGENCY PLANS

SUSTENET will implement a continuous risk management process with the aim of controlling potential threats, i.e., risk events that may negatively influence the objectives of the Action. This process includes the application of a risk assessment and a mitigation and contingency plan. Risk assessment includes both the identification of potential risks and the assessment of the potential impacts, probability and severity, of those risks. A risk mitigation and contingency plan describes certain actions designed to eliminate or minimize the impact of risk events, as well as the application of alternative methods to achieve the SUSTENET goals when identified risk events prevent the accomplishment of those goals. Action risks will be documented and registered within the SUSTENET Risk Register Table. As a first step, a provisory risk assessment is provided in Table 3. The risks are divided into 3 different categories: management risks, technical risks and long-term strategic risks. As part of the continuous risk management process that will be followed, the risks will be updated throughout the implementation of the Action at each MC meeting.

Table 3 – SUSTENET Risk Register Table describing a provisional risk assessment.

Description (level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: low/medium/high)	WGs	Mitigation and contingency plan
Management risks		
Inadequate communication between network participants/Action Members ((i) low, (ii) medium)	WG1-4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure that the adequate channels are maintained during the implementation of the Action (emails, online meetings, and reports). When necessary, define alternative communication channels.
Difficulty in involving YRs ((i) low, (ii) high)	WG1-4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Senior members will be encouraged to motivate younger researchers from their teams to be involved in the Action (e.g.: giving time for Action's tasks or mobility).
Technical risks		
Inability to produce devices containing sustainable TE materials ((i) medium, (ii) high)	1, 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimization of AI-assisted modelling activities. Constant interaction between WG1 and WG2 activities.
Insufficient level of dissemination and communication ((i) low, (ii) medium)	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Dissemination and Communication plan will be created, outlining the dissemination strategy that will include an index of relevant events and actions.
Insufficient level of attendance to the Action activities ((i) low, (ii) medium)	WG1-4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delegation of responsibilities to the different Action Members, to increase the commitment of all participants.
Long-term strategic risks		
Lack of stakeholder's interest ((i) low, (ii) high)	2, 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuous dialogue.
Lack of market demands ((i) medium, (ii) high)	2, 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create specific use cases by involving potential users.

4.1.4. GANTT DIAGRAM

		Year 1				Year 2				Year 3				Year 4			
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4												
Working Groups	WG1																
	Tasks																
	T1.1																
	T1.2																
	WG2																
	Tasks																
	T2.1																
	T2.2																
	T2.3																
	WG3																
	Tasks																
	T3.1																
	T3.2																
T3.3																	
WG4																	
Tasks																	
T4.1																	
T4.2																	
T4.3																	
Activities	Kick-off & final meeting	x															x
	MC Meetings	x				x				x				x			
	CG meetings	x		x		x		x		x		x		x		x	
	WG meetings	x		x		x		x		x		x		x		x	
	STSM		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
	Training				x				x				x			x	
	Workshop				x				x				x			x	
	Fostering Forums		x		x		x		x		x		x		x		x
	Webinars			x	x		x		x		x		x		x	x	
Conferences			x	x		x	x			x	x			x	x		
Deliverabl	D1	x															
	D2				x												
	D3				x												
	D4							x									

D5									x									
D6											x							
D7																		
D8																		
D9																		
D10																		
D11																		
D12																		
D13																		
D14																		
D15																		
D16																		x
D17																		x
D18																		x

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